

003A
GPS: Detrended and full GrAtSiD fit

GPS: Detrended and with seasonal and steps removed

Fluids: Detrended and full GrAtSiD fit

Fluids: Detrended and with seasonal and steps removed

Comparing Seasonals

028A
GPS: Detrended and full GrAtSiD fit

GPS: Detrended and with seasonal and steps removed

Fluids: Detrended and full GrAtSiD fit

Fluids: Detrended and with seasonal and steps removed

Comparing Seasonals

029A
GPS: Detrended and full GrAtSiD fit

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Comparing Seasonals

030A
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Comparing Seasonals

063A
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Fluids: Detrended and full GrAtSiD fit

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Comparing Seasonals

KALM
GPS: Detrended and full GrAtSiD fit

GPS: Detrended and with seasonal and steps removed

Fluids: Detrended and full GrAtSiD fit

Fluids: Detrended and with seasonal and steps removed

Comparing Seasonals

KORI
GPS: Detrended and full GrAtSiD fit

GPS: Detrended and with seasonal and steps removed

Fluids: Detrended and full GrAtSiD fit

Fluids: Detrended and with seasonal and steps removed

Comparing Seasonals

MOL1
GPS: Detrended and full GrAtSiD fit

GPS: Detrended and with seasonal and steps removed

Fluids: Detrended and full GrAtSiD fit

Fluids: Detrended and with seasonal and steps removed

Comparing Seasonals

NEAB
GPS: Detrended and full GrAtSiD fit

GPS: Detrended and with seasonal and steps removed

Fluids: Detrended and full GrAtSiD fit

Fluids: Detrended and with seasonal and steps removed

Comparing Seasonals

PAT0
GPS: Detrended and full GrAtSiD fit

GPS: Detrended and with seasonal and steps removed

Fluids: Detrended and full GrAtSiD fit

Fluids: Detrended and with seasonal and steps removed

Comparing Seasonals

PYL1
GPS: Detrended and full GrAtSiD fit

GPS: Detrended and with seasonal and steps removed

Fluids: Detrended and full GrAtSiD fit

Fluids: Detrended and with seasonal and steps removed

Comparing Seasonals

PYRG
GPS: Detrended and full GrAtSiD fit

GPS: Detrended and with seasonal and steps removed

Fluids: Detrended and full GrAtSiD fit

Fluids: Detrended and with seasonal and steps removed

Comparing Seasonals

RLSO
GPS: Detrended and full GrAtSiD fit

GPS: Detrended and with seasonal and steps removed

Fluids: Detrended and full GrAtSiD fit

Fluids: Detrended and with seasonal and steps removed

Comparing Seasonals

SPET
GPS: Detrended and full GrAtSiD fit

GPS: Detrended and with seasonal and steps removed

Fluids: Detrended and full GrAtSiD fit

Fluids: Detrended and with seasonal and steps removed

Comparing Seasonals

TRIP
GPS: Detrended and full GrAtSiD fit

GPS: Detrended and with seasonal and steps removed

Fluids: Detrended and full GrAtSiD fit

Fluids: Detrended and with seasonal and steps removed

Comparing Seasonals

VLSM
GPS: Detrended and full GrAtSiD fit

GPS: Detrended and with seasonal and steps removed

Fluids: Detrended and full GrAtSiD fit

Fluids: Detrended and with seasonal and steps removed

Comparing Seasonals

